

Supporting Information - Improving the reliability of cohesion policy databases

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Fig. 1: Convergence plot for Pdm.

Fig. 2: Convergence plot for AsV.

Fig. 3: Convergence plot for Lgr.

Fig. 4: Convergence plot for Lmb.

Fig. 5: Convergence plot for Abr.

Fig. 6: Convergence plot for MIs.

Fig. 7: Convergence plot for Cmp.

Fig. 8: Convergence plot for Apl.

Fig. 9: Convergence plot for Bsl.

Fig. 10: Convergence plot for Clb.

Fig. 11: Convergence plot for Scl.

Fig. 12: Convergence plot for Srd.

Convergence_plot_TNT.png

Fig. 13: Convergence plot for TAA.

Fig. 14: Convergence plot for Vnt.

Fig. 15: Convergence plot for FVG.

Fig. 16: Convergence plot for EmR.

Fig. 17: Convergence plot for Tsc.

Fig. 18: Convergence plot for Umb.

Fig. 19: Convergence plot for Laz.

Fig. 20: Convergence plot for Mrc.

Fig. 21: Distributions for Pdm, AsV, Lgr, Abr, Bsl, Clb, Scl, Srd, TAA, Vnt, Umb, acronym-next-pages Number of occurrences in the simulation against cumulative distance between the estimated and reported expenditures

Fig. 22: Conditional output distributions for Pdm when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 23: Conditional output distributions for AsV when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 24: Conditional output distributions for Lgr when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 25: Conditional output distributions for Lmb when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 26: Conditional output distributions for Abr when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 27: Conditional output distributions for Mls when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 28: Conditional output distributions for Cmp when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 29: Conditional output distributions for Apl when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 30: Conditional output distributions for Bsl when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 31: Conditional output distributions for Scl when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 32: Conditional output distributions for Srd when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 33: Conditional output distributions for TST when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 34: Conditional output distributions for Vnt when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 35: Conditional output distributions for FVG when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 36: Conditional output distributions for EmR when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 37: Conditional output distributions for Tsc when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 38: Conditional output distributions for Umb when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 39: Conditional output distributions for Mrc when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 40: Distributions of Pdm distance when the *residual selector* is fixed against the initial distribution

Fig. 41: Distributions of FVG distance when the *residual selector* is fixed against the initial distribution

Fig. 42: Distributions of FVG distance when the *residual selector* is fixed against the initial distribution

Fig. 43: Distributions of Lmb distance when the *residual selector* is fixed against the initial distribution

Fig. 44: Distributions of Abr distance when the *residual selector* is fixed against the initial distribution

Fig. 45: Distributions of Mls distance when the *residual selector* is fixed against the initial distribution

Fig. 46: Distributions of Cmp distance when the *residual selector* is fixed against the initial distribution

Fig. 47: Distributions of Apl distance when the *residual selector* is fixed against the initial distribution

Fig. 48: Distributions of Bsl distance when the *residual selector* is fixed against the initial distribution

Fig. 49: Distributions of Clb distance when the *residual selector* is fixed against the initial distribution

Fig. 50: Distributions of Scl distance when the *residual selector* is fixed against the initial distribution

Fig. 51: Distributions of Srd distance when the *residual selector* is fixed against the initial distribution

Fig. 52: Distributions of TST distance when the *residual selector* is fixed against the initial distribution